

SUCCESSFUL MANAGEMENT OF RADIAL NERVE PARALYSIS IN A 2-YEAR-OLD MONGREL

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ABSTRACT Background: Traumatic nerve injuries are quite common in small animal practice, and they are observed in animals of any age. A 2-year-old mongrel was presented to the Veterinary teaching hospital, the University of Ibadan with knuckling of the right forelimb. **Case Summary:** The client gave a history of an automobile accident. The animal was clinically evaluated with rectal temperature 38oC, heart rate of 80 beats/minutes and respiratory rate of 16. The animal resented the limb being touched. The case was managed therapeutically with Neurobion® which is a combination of vitamins B1, B6 and B12, Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) which was given by oral administration. The right fore-limb was placed in a plaster cast (POP) to discourage the use of the limb to avoid further use of the limb while cage rest was advised. The type of nerve injury encountered here falls under the classification of neuropraxia. Here, it presents as minor contusions or compression of the peripheral nerve with a temporary interruption in the transmission of electrical impulses that will typically resolve by 3 to 6 weeks. **Conclusion:** Finally, the use of plaster cast was to discourage active use of the limb, and an anti-inflammatory agent helped to restore the use of the limb quickly.

KEYWORDS Radial, Nerve, Paralysis, Neuropraxia.

Introduction

Traumatic nerve injuries are quite common in small animal practice, and they are observed in animals of any age [1]. Nerve injuries can take the form of a neuropraxia, which presents as minor contusions or compression of the peripheral nerve with a temporary interruption in the transmission of electrical impulses that will typically resolve by 3 to 6 weeks [2]. Axonotmesis is a more severe form of nerve injury with damage to the axons themselves and accompanying distal Wallerian degeneration, but maintaining preservation of Schwann cells and an intact endoneurial nerve structure. The most severe form of damage is neurotmesis, where there is a complete anatomical disruption to nerve continuity; the proliferation of fibrous tissue and Schwann cells and axonal growth result in loss of nerve architecture and

function [3]. Here there is no possibility of spontaneous nerve recovery, and surgery is always necessary [4].

Peripheral nerve damages have also been classified according to their degree of severity. First-degree damage causes generation and conduction blockage at the site of injury with all the components of the nerve being intact. Second-degree damage is characterized by axonal disruption and Wallerian degeneration, while third-degree damage is accompanied by disruption of the axon and its related endoneurial tube. In fourth-degree damage, epineurium is the only structure that remains intact. Fifth-degree damage is the complete severance of all the nerve structures [5].

The radial nerve is the most frequently injured significant nerve in the upper limb. The radial nerve is 1 of 2 terminal branches of the posterior cord of the brachial plexus. It is posterior to the axillary artery at the shoulder, and branches away from the axillary nerve proximal to the quadrangular space before passing through the triangular space. The nerve travels laterally deep to the long head of the triceps muscle and lies between the lateral and the medial heads of the triceps at the spiral groove. The radial nerve innervates the triceps before piercing the lateral intermuscular septum and entering the anterior compartment [6].

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Most affected animals so managed usually have the affected limb(s) amputated or are eventually euthanized out of frustration of both the client and the attending veterinarian [7, 8]. Invaluable patients like a guide, guard, hunting, sport or indeed intimate pets, these options are often unacceptable to most clients. Therefore, some alternative treatment options with better prognoses are usually required.

Case report

Table 1 Timeline.

Dates	Medical history	Diagnostic testing	Interventions
	No previous case	None	None
	Automobile accident	Physical and clinical examination Respiratory rate, Heart rate, Rectal temperature	Drug therapy Plaster cast (POP)

The limb was examined for fracture, but none was found except for some tenderness which might have resulted from soft tissue injury. A 2-year-old mongrel was presented to the Veterinary teaching hospital, the University of Ibadan with knuckling of the right forelimb. The client gave a history of an automobile accident. The animal was clinically evaluated with rectal temperature 38°C, heart rate of 80 beats/minutes and respiratory rate of 16. The animal resented the limb being touched. All the vital parameters were within the normal range.

The case was managed therapeutically with Neurobion® which is a combination of vitamins B1, B6 and B12, Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID). The oral administration gave phenylbutazone at a dose rate of 3mg/kg. The right fore-limb was placed in a plaster cast (POP) to discourage the use of the limb to avoid further use of the limb while cage rest was advised. The dog was asked to be brought back in two weeks. After two weeks, the animal was examined, and all physiological parameters were within the normal range. The plaster cast was removed, and tenderness of the soft tissue had resolved. There was no resentment to touch of the paw. The dog has walked around, and remarkably the paw knuckling had disappeared. Furthermore, one-week cage rest was advised to avoid the overzealous use of the affected limb, hence precipitating recurrence.

Discussion and Conclusion

The radial nerve is most frequently injured in association with humeral fractures. The nerve can be injured by the fracture itself, during manipulation of the fragments during reduction/surgery or through entrapment by healing callus formation. Fractures of the radial head and neck and radius/ulna fractures can damage the posterior interosseous nerve [9, 10].

Acute peripheral nerve injury in small animals most often occurs as a result of trauma. The common types of trauma include automobile accidents, gunshots, bite wounds, lacerations and iatrogenic damage during surgical procedures, application of splints or casts and injection of therapeutic agents [1]. The

Figure 1: Dog presented with radial nerve paralysis.

Figure 2: Application of plaster cast.

Figure 3: Three weeks after the accident.

primary cause of the radial nerve paralysis, in this case, reported appears to be trauma due to the automobile accidents.

It has been shown in humans [11, 12] and animals [8, 7, 13] that certain peripheral neuropathies associated with locomotor dysfunction can be relieved by their location of the tendon of some functional and innervated muscle/tendon to the muscle/tendon which has been denervated as a result of nerve damage. These techniques have been used mainly in the management of radial paralysis in the fore-limbs of animals [14, 15]. The type of nerve injury encountered in this case falls under the classification of neuropraxia. Here, it presents as minor contusions or compression of the peripheral nerve with a temporary interruption in the transmission of electrical impulses that will typically resolve by 3 to 6 weeks [2]. The absence of fracture or severe soft tissue damage made the case to resolve quickly and thereby making the animal regain early use of the affected limb. It should be noted that enforced rest made the case to enjoy early resolution without which it could have advanced to Axonotmesis stage which is a more severe form of nerve injury with damage to the axons themselves and accompanying distal Wallerian degeneration, but maintaining preservation of Schwann cells and an intact endoneurial nerve structure. Also, the use of NSAID was of value since the anti-inflammatory effect helps to quickly remove the swelling of the limb due to the automobile accident. Finally, the use of plaster cast to discourage active use of the limb and an anti-inflammatory agent helped to restore the use of the limb quickly. The dog was presented in the third week and examination; the initial pain response has been abolished. The placement of the foot has become normal, and the animal walked without limping.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

REFERENCES

1. Antolitou A, Kazakos G, Prasinou N.N (2012) Peripheral nerve damage in companion animals Hellenic. Journal of Companion Animal Medicine; 1 (2): 12-19.
2. Swaim SF. Peripheral Nerve Surgery. In: Veterinary Neurology. Oliver JE, Hoerlein BF, Mayhew IG (eds). Saunders: Philadelphia, 1987, pp. 493-512.
3. Rodkey WG (1993). Peripheral nerve surgery. In: Disease Mechanisms in Small Animal Surgery. Bojrab MJ (ed). Lea & Febiger: Philadelphia, pp. 1135-1141.
4. Seddon H (1943). Three types of nerve injury. Brain; 66:237-288.
5. Sunderland S (1968). Nerves and Nerve Injuries. Williams & Wilkins: Baltimore, 1968, pp. 808-885.
6. Karin L. Ljungquist, MD, Paul Martineau, MD, Christopher A (2015) Radial Nerve Injuries J Hand Surg Am. 2015; 40(1):166e172
7. Hart, A. H. and Tremblay, J. A. (1982). Tendon transplanting and re-training- A surgical procedure to correct functional loss that usually results in amputation. Vet. Med./Small Anim. Clin. 919 – 921

8. Bennett, D., & Vaughan, L. C. (1976a). The use of muscle relocation techniques in the treatment of peripheral nerve paralysis in dogs and cats. J. Small. Anim. Pract. 17, 99-108.
9. Serrano KD, Rebella GS, Sansone JM, Kim MK (2012). A rare case of posterior interosseous nerve palsy associated with radial head fracture. J Emerg Med 2012; 43:e115-e117.
10. Li H, Cai QX, Shen PQ, et al. (2013) Posterior interosseous nerve entrapment after Monteggia fracture-dislocation in children. Chin J Traumatol 2013; 16:131-135.
11. Wapner, K. L., Pavlock, G. S., Hecht, P. J., Nasali, F., & Walther, R. (1993). Repair of chronic Achilles Tendon rupture with Hallicus longus tendon transfer. Foot Ankle 14,443-449.
12. Bradon J. W, Harris G. (2015) Tendon Transfers –Medscape:emedicine.medscape.com/article/1245758-overview.
13. Leighton, R. L. (1982). Tendon transfer for the treatment of peroneal paralysis in a dog. Report of a case. Vet. Surg., 11: (2), 65-67.
14. Hussain, S., & Petit, G. A. (1967). Tendon transplantation to compensate for Radial Nerve paralysis in the dog. Amer.Journ Vet. Res., 28(123), 334-335.
15. Bacher, J. D., & Potlay, S. (1976). Radial paralysis in a goat: Treatment by tendon transposition. Vet Med/Small Anim. Clin.1031-1034.